

The Role of Women in IT and Society in Uzbekistan

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ABSTRACT:

The participation of women in the field of information technology is becoming significant topic across Uzbekistan, and research on this topic is becoming more and more relevant not only in Uzbekistan but across the Central Asia. The aim of this paper delves into analyzing the factors affecting to increase of number of women in IT professions as well as focuses on the role of women in the IT industry, their influence on technology development and benefits they bring to Uzbekistan. The IT field is in significant demand in today's world, and many companies require qualified specialists. The quantity of women in this field is increasing gradually due to improvements such as creation special programs for representatives of female gender.

Keywords: IT, women in IT industry, CS, Uzbekistan, gender equality, women's rights.

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INTRODUCTION

The statement about the true equality of women and men is considered in the modern world as the basis of social progress, a sustainable developed society. Everyone knows that over the years of independent development, a weighty legislative and organizational base has been created in the country, aimed at strengthening the role and status of women, their social protection. The country has adopted gender-oriented laws, more than 20 decrees and resolutions of the president and government regulating the protection of women's rights and freedoms. This allows the beautiful half of humanity to work more efficiently [1]. As a result, their role in the development of society is becoming more active. The focus on gender equality also supports Uzbekistan's ambition to be a regional IT hub. Under the Government's leadership, both the public and private sector have put substantial effort and resources into the country's IT prowess. This has included the opening of the IT Park in Tashkent to create a critical mass of IT talent in a single location. Another significant initiative in the country has been the establishment of the Astrum Academy which trains young talents in programming and big data analytics [2]. Encouraging girls to be educated is an important step that is long-sighted. In addition to the fact that today's student girl will become a mature specialist in her field tomorrow, she will also become a mother with a scientific, intellectual potential, raising a child with a broad worldview. An enlightened woman makes a worthy contribution to the adoption of the right decision, which is inherent in the future, both in her field and in the family [3]. The understanding of the benefits is provided in this article by discussing some common reasons why it is important for Uzbek women to pursue a career in IT field and their role in it.

The Situation in the Country and the Legislative Environment

Uzbekistan has a rich and ancient culture, which has been influenced by many traditions over the centuries. Due to the importance of the main cities of modern Uzbekistan, located along the Silk Road, continues to play the role of a bridge connecting East and West. In many ways, this situation is reflected in modern gender relations, in which Uzbek women have achieved success in a number of professional fields, although a deeply established traditional view remains about women, first of all, as keepers of the hearth and playing a subordinate role.

Gender Aspects in the Transition Period

In 2011 Uzbekistan has celebrated the 20th anniversary of independence. The transition process has not been smooth for all countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States, and Uzbekistan has also experienced both positive and negative developments in terms of gender equality. The situation of women and men in Uzbekistan is influenced by the fact that the country has undergone significant and rapid changes in recent years.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Alieva Nodira Makhkampulatovna and Abdurashidova Sabina discuss in their article that in Eastern culture, women have always been cherished as companions, partners, wise and compassionate individuals, and as the nurturers of family harmony. Philosophers have acknowledged the vital role of women in both the household and wider community, emphasizing their significance in raising and guiding children. Abu Rayhan Beruni in his views attached special importance to the fact that the family world is directly in the hands of intelligent, insightful, and well-mannered women. The enlightened sage Abdullah Avloni states: girls should strive for knowledge more than anyone else, because with this knowledge they educate the next generation. "There are several important factors that influence women's progress in science. These factors include their motivation, learning methods, and interest in learning. The goals that women set for themselves and the way they go about achieving them ensure their interest in learning and faith in science. The next important factor is teaching methods and technologies. It can be easier and more fun for women to pursue science through tools such as online platforms, videos, and interactive textbooks. These methods make the learning process convenient and effective. In addition, a learning environment is very important for women. For studying, it is necessary to use resources such as environment, books, and electronic libraries. This learning environment increases their motivation and facilitates the learning process.

Asian Development Bank in the book "Uzbekistan Gender assessment by country" indicates that although the reform procedures did include measures to enhance economic opportunities for women in Uzbekistan, the endeavors to advocate for gender equality were often separate from the country's development schemes. Typically, initiatives to promote gender equality concentrated on enhancing women's access to fundamental resources, involvement in decision-making processes, improving maternal healthcare, and combating domestic violence in 2014 Data from annual assessments of the degree of equality between men and women in Uzbekistan showed that, despite consistently high rates of equal access for women Uzbekistan's access to education and the results of health protection measures, progress made in the political empowerment of women, as well as in their access to economic opportunities, was somewhat limited. In practice, the term "gender" was not yet widely applicable in Uzbekistan, in particular, it was not yet widely used by the governing circles. This term was mostly considered synonymous with the word "women", and work focused on gender equality was often associated with solving only social problems. Gender equality was mainly perceived as a process of ensuring justice and impartiality towards women, but was not yet recognized as a prerequisite for further economic growth and stability of the country. Gender roles and norms The National Action Plan for the implementation of the recommendations of the Committee of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), approved in 2010, focuses on the need to eliminate stereotypes regarding traditional gender roles in the Uzbek family and society. Not being a part of any law or policy, ideas about the traditional role of women related to motherhood, children and family prevail, often with the inequality of the public role of women in public positions or in business. These patriarchal values became more pronounced after the acquisition Uzbekistan's independence. But this does not mean that such a situation implies the impossibility of changing these cultural norms. It is necessary to consider the likelihood of the most effective overcoming of stereotypes in activities aimed at achieving gender equality. Projects should include measures to promote a more equitable model of gender relations and expand concepts regarding the role of women in society [4].

Anvar Meliboev in his work "Yosh ayollar O'zbekistonda axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari sohasi rivojining kalitimi?" presents the fact that the Government of Uzbekistan made a decision "to create favorable conditions for the creation and development of high-tech production, to further deepen the integration of science, education and production processes" The industry influences the

resolution of key social problems such as education, health and poverty eradication, which are important elements of Sustainable Development Goals set for 2030. The groups focusing on these issues are supported by women working in the ICT sector in Uzbekistan. Participants of the event visited their companies, formed collaborative skills and strengthened valuable mentoring relationships with business models. Even after the end of the event, they retain this opportunity. Already on the Facebook page of the program came messages of interest from almost all regions of Uzbekistan. One person passed the online curriculum independently and developed a mobile app for older people, which received special recognition from the program's judges. After the success of the Technovation Challenge in Tashkent, the Uzbekistan women's Committee and the Association for the support of children and families now intend to repeat it nationwide. Studies show that reducing the gap between male and female employment has been an important factor in economic growth. We believe that this situation creates favorable conditions, creates more equitable opportunities for women and contributes to economic growth for Uzbekistan. Because there can not be any reasons for why the next Margaret Hamilton or Catherine Johnson will not be from exactly Uzbekistan.

METHODOLOGY

The methods of studying existing scientific research articles on the role of women in Uzbekistan, study of statistical data, comparison and analysis, data grouping, are widely used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is gratifying that the number of students currently studying in higher education institutions of our country exceeds 1 million, of which the share of women is 47.8 percent and is growing from year to year. In the academic year 2022/2023, women made up 49.3% of the total students admitted to higher education institutions. This was 37.9 percent in 2017 and 39.6 percent in 2018 [3]. Statistics on the proportion of women using the internet among 10 and older based on the agency's household sampling observations data, January 2023 as of December, it was 87.3%. In 2021 it comprised 72.6%, in 2022 - 81.0% [6]. The head of our state, on which the process of reforming all spheres of life of the country and society is based. Its main content is the protection of human rights and interests, the growth of the standard of living of the people, ensuring employment and increasing the labor motivation of citizens. As part of the implementation of socio-economic policy, special attention is paid to the issues of legal, economic and social protection of women, the creation of they need the necessary conditions to further enhance their role in society. It is worth noting that the protection of women's rights and interests in Uzbekistan has been elevated to the rank of state policy. It is aimed at affirming the principle of equal rights and freedoms, creating equal opportunities for all, regardless of gender. And every woman who feels the strength, energy and knowledge in herself can take full advantage of them, which she can use both for the harmonious development of her personality and for the prosperity of the country. "Large-scale work is being carried out in the country to increase the socio-political activity of women, to demonstrate their talent and abilities in various fields, to ensure strict observance of their rights and legitimate interests, as well as to strengthen the institution of the family," stressed Tanzila Narbayeva, Deputy Prime Minister, Chairman of the Women's Committee Uzbekistan. After the panel discussions, the conference participants agreed to develop a strategy to increase the number of women in industries where their participation is insignificant or completely absent. Conference participants also recognized the need to develop a set of measures to create jobs for girls and women with disabilities, study experience in the field of entrepreneurship development, artistic, scientific, technical and national creativity among women, discuss partnerships and sign memoranda between the Women's Committee Uzbekistan and the main organizations of the Government and non-governmental organizations dealing with women's issues in Uzbekistan Central Asia and other developed countries that were the focus of the conference [7]. In 2021, 7 of Uzbekistan's women are academicians, 271 are doctors of science (DSC), and 1,411 are holders of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) degrees. Uzbek scientists are especially actively looking for such areas as Chemistry, Biotechnology, Agriculture. The participation of our women in the development of education, health, social and humanitarian spheres plays a significant role. The country's State Agency reported that according to the results of the 2022-2023 academic

year, more than 7.9 thousand women in Uzbekistan received a master's degree. As it can be concluded, in comparison to 2018 year in which the rate of women admitted to high educational institutions was only 39.6, in 2022/2023 it increased up to 49.3.

CONCLUSION

From ancient times the role of women in society has been significant factor for achieving balance in family as well as for ensuring that women can educate the next generation if they get high quality education and the gender imbalance is eliminated. Factors such as convenient environment, electronical books and etc. play crucial role in ensuring that women get knowledge. Gender equality was firstly seen as a way to promote fairness and equality for women, rather than being understood as essential for driving economic growth and maintaining a stable society. Still, the National Action Plan, endorsed in 2010, emphasizes the importance of eradicating stereotypes related to traditional gender roles within Uzbek families and society, as outlined in the recommendations of the Committee of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW). Additionally, The Uzbekistan government has opted to facilitate the establishment and growth of advanced technological industries to enhance the amalgamation of scientific, educational, and production procedures. This industry plays a vital role in addressing significant social challenges such as education, healthcare, and poverty elimination, aligning with the Sustainable Development Goals set for 2030.

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